

Reducing Input in Forest Operations: A Valuable Opportunity for Carbon Credit Generation

Introduction

Forest carbon credit additionality projects are initiatives aimed at generating carbon credits through sustainable forest management and conservation activities. These carbon credits are then used in carbon markets to offset greenhouse gas emissions from companies or individuals. Typically, these projects focus on sustainable forest management practices that enhance carbon sequestration within forests, known as "additionality," achieved through activities like silviculture treatments that differ from previous management practises (e.g. conversion between coppices to high forest, enlarging the cut periods, fire-preventions).

In the context of carbon emissions, it is not only essential to create additionality projects but also to reduce emissions. Forest operations can contribute to emissions and pollution, even in the context of additionality carbon credit projects. Therefore, employing a "Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)," a systematic and comprehensive methodology used to evaluate the environmental impact of processes, becomes crucial. This assessment helps evaluate the environmental sustainability of forest operations, compare them to the "business as usual (BAU)" scenario, and identify opportunities to reduce emissions. This, in turn, enhances the effectiveness of additionality projects in generating more carbon credits.

Within the context of the CO2MARCHE OG as an additionality project for carbon credit generation, a methodology has been created to quantify the reduction of energetic inputs in forest operations to generate additional carbon credits. Through this analysis, electric chainsaws and the use of alkylated gasoline have been identified as means to reduce emissions from forest operations when compared to traditional gasoline-powered equipment.

In this context, it is also possible to calculate the additionality produced by more sustainable forest operations, leading to the creation of more additionality credits compared to traditional forest operations carried out with traditional gasoline or chainsaws. In this context, CO2MARCHE works within the framework of Sustainable Forest Management certification under the PEFC standard to set-up the methodology to quantify the additionality carbon credit generate by reduction emission of forest operations via a rigorous LCA that contrasts the BAU scenario with the new, more sustainable tools. Ultimately, if forest operations demonstrate greater sustainability in terms of emissions, forest owners and forest operation companies can generate more

carbon credits, resulting in increased revenue. This revenue can not only cover equipment costs but also have a positive impact on the environment as a whole.

Lessons learned

To combat climate change, it is essential to reduce emissions, and within the context of an operational group dealing with CO₂ and carbon credits in the forestry sector, it has proven to be of paramount importance to also strive to reduce emissions stemming from forestry operations. Through the use of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, it is possible to calculate the Business As Usual (BAU) for forestry activities and promote the use of machinery or fuels with a lower environmental impact. This is crucial, especially in the context of climate change mitigation, to lower greenhouse gas emissions. Besides providing an environmental benefit, this can also lead to the generation of more credits in an additionality project, potentially resulting in greater financial gain as the generated credits are greater.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.co2marche.it/>

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